

Population and % control of rice hispa at different intervals^a after pesticide applications, Muridkey, Pakistan.

Insecticide and formulation	Dose (kg ai/ha)	Application method	Av no. of alive hispa adults/5 rice plants at						Percent control of hispa at				
			BA	1 DAA	3 DAA	10 DAA	20 DAA	30 DAA	1 DAA	3 DAA	10 DAA	20 DAA	30 DAA
Diazinon 60 EC	1.125	Spray	89	13 c	10 e-g	33 c	62 c	91 ab	85	88	63	30	-2
Fenitrothion 20 EC	0.500	Spray	89	9 c	7 f-h	7 f-h	30 d	65 c-e	89	92	92	66	27
Malathion 57 EC	1.425	Spray	88	16 c	15 e	35 c	70 b	85 a-c	81	83	60	20	3
Phosphamidon 50 EC	0.688	Spray	90	7 c	5 f-h	14 d	37 d	75 b-d	92	94	84	59	16
BHC 10 D	0.500	Dust	86	8 c	7 f-h	9 e-f	11 f	14 hi	91	92	89	87	84
BHC 10 D	0.750	Dust 91		2 c	2 h	1 i	2 h	4 i	98	98	99	98	96
BHC (10 D) + DDT (10 D) in 1:3 mixture	0.312 +0.937	Dust	83	4 c	4 gh	5 g-i	7 f-h	15 hi	95	95	94	92	81
Carbaryl 10 D	2.500	Dust	91	4 c	3 gh	9 fg	19 e	44 e-g	95	96	90	79	21
Cotton dust ^c (6.3% BHC + 10.4% DDT + 83.3% sulfur	7.200	Dust	90	8 c	15 e	13 d	21 e	31 f-h	91	83	85	77	66
DDT 10 D	0.750	Dust	86	7 c	6 f-h	6 f-h	10 fg	18 hi	92	93	93	88	79
Pyridaphenthion 2D	0.800	Dust	92	11 c	12 ef	15 d	21 e	53 d-f	88	87	84	77	42
Carbofuran 3 G	0.750	Broadcast	90	83 ab	29 d	9 fg	7 f-h	22 g-i	8	68	91	92	76
Carbofuran 3 G	1.125	Broadcast	87	73 b	24 d	4 hi	3 gh	5 hi	16	72	95	97	94
Cartap 10 G	1.250	Broadcast	90	79 ab	41 c	8 f-h	7 f-h	27 g-i	12	54	91	92	70
Diazinon 10 G	2.000	Broadcast	87	82 ab	67 b	52 b	37 d	65 c-e	6	23	40	57	24
Control	-	-	90	90 a	93 a	98 a	97 a	101 a	0	-4	-10	-8	13
LSD at 5%				14	7	4	7	24					

^aBA = before application. DAA = d after application. ^bIn a column, averages followed by common letters are significantly similar at 95% level of confidence. ^cCotton dust is a brand name for BHC + DDT + sulfur mixture formulated by Ittehad Pesticides Ltd., Pakistan.

Pest control and management OTHER PESTS

Control of root-knot nematode in upland rice

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Root-knot nematode *Meloidogyne incognita* is an important upland rice pathogen in Nigeria. Infected plants are stunted and leaves become chlorotic. Roots have fewer root hairs and galls are formed.

Chemical seed treatment was tested for nematode control on variety FARO 11. Rice was grown in plastic pots in autoclaved sandy-loam soil under simulated upland conditions in the screenhouse. Each pot was inoculated with 1,500 *M. incognita* eggs at planting. Roots were washed free of soil at the end of the experiment and scored for galling, and the nematodes in a 200-g soil sample from each pot were counted.

Carbofuran was most effective in protecting the seedlings from root-knot nematode. Seed treated with PCNB and

carbofuran had early seedling emergence (see table). PCNB, phenthoate, and EPN provided the best seedling protection against secondary pathogen infection, as indicated by the leaf damage index. All the test chemicals except phenthoate performed better than the control. EPN, however, is suspected to be phytotoxic. □

Chemical seed treatment for control of *M. incognita* in upland rice, Ibadan, Nigeria.^a

Seed treatment	Rate (ai/ha)	Plant ht (cm) 14 DAS	Seedling vigor ^b 14 DAS	Leaf damage index (14 DAS)	Root galling index ^c	Final nematode count
Disulfoton	1 kg	14.70	7	4	4	1100
PCNB	40 g	19.83	6	2	3	1150
Carbofuran	1 kg	19.13	5	3	1	550
Phenthoate	0.75 kg	13.23	7	2	4	2700
EPN	0.50 kg	8.20	7	2	2	850
Control	-	13.40	7	5	5	2825

^aMean of 3 replications. DAS = days after seeding. ^bAfter the 1980 Standard Evaluation System for Rice. ^cAfter an international *Meloidogyne* project.

Effect of zinc on stem nematode-infected rice

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We studied the effect of Zn application on stem nematode-infected rice plants. Sixteen pots, each with 8 kg moist Zn-deficient soil (0.6 ppm), were fertilized with 200-66-83 kg NPK. Eight of the pots were fertilized with 50 ppm Zn as ZnSO₄. Four germinated seeds of BR3

were planted in each pot. BR3 is susceptible to Zn deficiency and ufra disease caused by the stem nematode *Ditylenchus angustus* (Butler) Filipjev. Pots were irrigated with pond water with no Zn contamination. Symptoms of Zn deficiency in plants grown in pots without added Zn were observed 20 d after planting.

Plants from 4 pots of each group (with and without added Zn) were inoculated with 200 ufra nematodes/plant, 25 and 35 d after planting, by seedling base and sheath inoculation methods. Immediately after inoculation, the plants were covered with polyethylene bags for 72 h to increase humidity. Soil in the pots was always submerged.

Splash-patterned chlorosis developed 2 to 4 wk after inoculation, followed by

Zn content of plant and soil, and its effect on stem nematode-infected rice plants, BRRI.^a

Treatment ^b	Zn content (ppm)			Fertile tillers (%)	UI (%)	UII (%)	Filled grains per panicle (%)	Av yield (g/pot)	Nematode multiplication rate at panicle initiation
	In soil		In plant at harvest						
	Initial	Final							
Without added Zn	0.6	0.5	25.3	15.1	75.7	24.3	8.8	0.7	1:14
With added Zn	0.6	3.8	39.3	28.5	62.6	37.4	30.0	2.1	1:12
't' value ^c			9.2**	2.6*	3.9**	3.9**	4.1**	2.5*	0.3 ns

^aFigures are av of 4 replications. ^bZn was added as ZnSO₄ (50 ppm) at transplanting and the plants were inoculated with nematode, at 25 and 35 d after transplanting, by seedling base and sheath inoculation methods. ^c** = 1% level of significance, * = 5% level of significance, ns = not significant.

other ufra symptoms such as yellowing and twisting and crinkling of younger leaves. There were two different patterns of panicle emergence: panicles fully enclosed within the flag leaf sheath (UI), and partially emerged panicles with a few

filled grains at the tip (UII).

Zn-deficient plants had less fertile tillers, fewer filled grains, and more severe ufra symptoms than plants with added Zn (see table). □

Incidence of rice root nematode in Madurai

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The rice root nematode *Hirschmanniella* sp. significantly reduces rice growth and yield in India. We surveyed 33 blocks of Madurai district for rice root nematode incidence in 1981-82 and 1982-83.

IR20 and Ponni are the rice varieties grown in the area in samba. Root samples were collected from active tillering phase to heading from eight randomly selected fields from four villages per block. Ten 5-g root samples were taken from randomly selected clumps in each field and processed by the Baermann funnel technique. The population of rice root nematodes *H. oryzae* and *H. mucronata* was recorded. Damage level was considered to be more than 250 nematodes/5-g root.

Rice root nematode was found in all areas surveyed. Populations ranged from 49 to 521 nematodes/5 g of root. Infestation was most severe in Cumbum tract of the Periyar Irrigation Project, and popula-

tion was above damage level in Alanganaloor, Bodi, Chinnamanoor, Cumbum, Dindigul, Palani, Periyakulam, Sanarpatti, Theni, Usilampatti, and Uthamapalayam. □

TKM9 is resistant to rice-root nematode

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IR20, IR50, Paiyur 1, and TKM9 were evaluated at different growth stages for resistance to rice-root nematode *Hirschmanniella oryzae*.

TKM9 was resistant to nematodes at all growth stages (see table). IR50 was more resistant than IR20 and Paiyur 1.

Rice varietal resistance to rice root nematode, Kancheepuram, India.

Variety	Nematode population in 2 g of root			
	Planting	30 d after transplanting	Boot leaf	Harvest
IR20	5	20	50	35
IR50	5	—	5	25
Palyur 1	30	240	10	10
TKM9	—	—	—	—

Insecticide root dip controls rice root nematode

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We evaluated insecticide root dips for control of rice root nematode *Hirschmanniella oryzae* during navarai season.

IR50 seedlings were dipped in 0.02% solutions of phosphamidon, chlorpyrifos, or monocrotophos for 20 min before planting.

Phosphamidon and chlorpyrifos root dips reduced the nematode population 30 d after transplanting (see table). □

Insecticide root dips evaluated for rice root nematode control at Kancheepuram, India.

Insecticide (0.02% solution)	Nematodes/2 g root
Phosphamidon	0.83
Chlorpyrifos	0.83
Monocrotophos	1.66
No treatment	5.83

SE = 0.34